

H2020: Microwave Microscopy for Advanced and Efficient Materials Analysis and Production

Ayming, Business Performance Consulting Group, is supporting [MMAMA project](#) (*Microwave Microscopy for Advanced and Efficient Materials Analysis and Production*), which will offer a nanoscale characterization platform for the European manufacturers of coatings, photovoltaic cells, and semi-conductor circuits. Partners of the project will use a combination of scanning microwave microscopes, dielectric resonators, and simulation to measure the material and interface properties of complicated material systems and nano-structures.

This project, launched on November 1, 2017, will last 3 years. It received a European funding of € 3.99 million, allocated by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

During the [Microwave and Radar week 2020](#) (Vilnius, Lithuania), on Monday 18 May 2020, MMAMA will organise a dedicated half-day workshop: *“Material and Impedance Measurement Techniques in the Project MMAMA”*.

The chairs of the event are: Dr. Johannes Hoffmann, METAS (Switzerland), Dr. Malgorzata Celuch, QWED (Poland).

The MMAMA partners will share project results and discuss about up-to-date innovations in the area.

To access the [detailed agenda of the workshop](#).

Registration is available on the [main website of MIKON](#).

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement MMAMA n° 761036.

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